

PROPERTIES OF REINFORCED ALUMINIUM FOUNDRY ALLOYS

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Summary

Aluminium foundry alloys such as Al-Si12-Cu-Ni find their applications in the car industry. The requirement of this industry for higher performance materials will lead to a development of new aluminium alloys able to withstand higher temperatures. Metal matrix composites seem to be suitable candidates for those higher performance duties. The purpose of this work is to evaluate the behaviour of Al-Si12-Cu-Ni reinforced by alumina based fibers or by silicon carbide whiskers. The composites are prepared by squeeze casting. Mechanical properties are evaluated at different temperatures up to 350°C.

Introduction

The requirements of the engine manufacturers : fuel saving, ,reducing exhaust emissions and noise, increasing performances and reliability, lead to higher sollicitations on components. High temperature behaviours of materials have to be improved.

In the particular case of aluminium alloys, reinforcement by ceramic fibers is a very promissing way to achieve this goal (1).

This study deals with the mechanical characterisation of metal matrix composites. Those composites, based on an aluminium-silicon commercial alloy and on short ceramic fibers, are manufactured by squeeze casting (2-3).

Experimental procedures

Composite manufacturing. The alloy used for this study is an aluminium silicon alloy : Al-Si12-Cu-Ni. Table I shows the standard composition of such alloys.

Table I. Standard composition for Al-Si12-Cu-Ni alloys

Si	Fe	Cu	Zn	Mg	Mn	Ni	Pb	Sn	Ti
11.5-13.0	<0.8	1.0-1.5	<0.2	1-1.5	<0.5	0.8-1.2	<0.1	<0.05	<0.1

The fibers which have been selected on the basis of their mechanical properties, chemical compatibility with liquid aluminium alloys and availability on the market to reinforce this alloy are :

- . an alumina based fiber manufactured by I.C.I. named "SAFFIL " grade RF
- . silicon carbide whiskers "TOKAMAX" obtained from TOKAI CARBON -

Properties of individual fibers are summarized in table II.

Table II. Properties of fibers used in this work

	UTS (MPa)	Elastic modulus (GPa)	Réf
I.C.I. SAFFIL	2000	300	4
TOKAY TOKAMAX	3-14000	400-700	5

Different volume fractions of fibers are tested as summarized in table III.

Table III. Type of reinforcement used and volume fraction

I.C.I. SAFFIL	0.05	0.12	0.20
TOKAI SiC whiskers	0.12	0.16	0.20

Infiltration of the fibers is made by squeeze casting. Fibers inserts of the different materials and volume fractions are placed in a mold which is preheated to 200°C. The metal is then poured at 750°C. Infiltration is obtained by applying pressure up to 1500 bars. The shape of the fiber inserts and of the parts which are obtained are illustrated in figure 1. A schematic of the squeeze casting process is shown in figure 2. Reference specimen without fibers are cast using the same process. All parts are stabilised 4 hours at 235 °C. The parts are then machined for metallographic inspection and evaluation of mechanical properties; tensile test specimen are machined out of the reinforced section.

Fig. 1 Fiber inserts and parts obtained (dimensions in mm)

Fig. 2 Squeeze casting operation

Testing procedures. The mechanical properties at room temperature are evaluated by testing 4 specimen for each configuration. The measured properties are : yield stress, U.T.S., elongation and Young's modulus. The fatigue properties are evaluated only on the highest level of reinforcement (20 % vf).

High temperature tests are performed after holding the specimen for 500 hours at temperature prior to testing at temperature. All tests are performed on an Instron machine at a rate of 1 mm/mn.

Results and discussions

Room temperature properties. Tensile test data are shown in tables IV, V and in figures 3,4.

Table IV. Tensile data obtained on SAFFIL reinforced Al-Si12-Cu-Ni

Vf	YS	s	w	UTS	s	w	E	s	w
0	210	3,8	9,5	297	1,8	3,5	71,9	4,5	13
0,05	232	4,2	10,4	282	6,5	15,1	78,4	2,3	6
0,12	251,5	14,6	38,3	273	19,6	49,6	83	7,8	21
0,20	282,5	11,3	25,2	312	16	42,3	95,2	2,7	7

Table V. Tensile data obtained on SiC whiskers reinforced Al-Si12-Cu-Ni

Vf	YS	s	w	UTS	s	w	E	s	w
0	210	3,8	9,5	297	1,8	3,5	71,9	4,5	13
0,12	266,5	4,2	10,6	359	33,6	85,6	95,3	1,6	6
0,16	264,5	0,6	1,6	374	8	23	90	3,7	9
0,20	298	4	10,2	383,6	15,2	38,8	111	5	13

In table IV and V the different variables are :

- Vf : volume fraction of fibers
- YS : 0,2 % yield stress (MPa)
- U.T.S. : ultimate tensile strength (MPa)
- E : Young's modulus (GPa)
- s : standard deviation
- w : range of measurements

Fig.3 UTS, yield stress and Young's modulus of Al-Si12-Cu-Ni reinforced with ICI SAFFIL as a function of volume fraction of fibers

Fig.4 UTS, yield stress and Young's modulus of Al-Si12-Cu-Ni reinforced with SiC whiskers (TOKAY) as a function of volume fraction of whiskers

Tables IV and V show average values, standard deviation and range of measurements (i.e. difference between highest and lowest values). A statistical analysis is made in order to check whether two average values are different or not at a given significant level. If we want to check the influence of a factor F on a property P, we give two values to F : F1, F2 and obtain average values P1 and P2 for P. We then compare P1 and P2 (statistical tables are available) at different significant level. If P1 and P2 are not different, we cannot draw any conclusion about F. If P1 and P2 are different at a significant level of 5 %, we shall say that the effect of F is "significant". If the significant level chosen is 1 %, the effect of F would be "highly significant" and lastly if the significant level chosen is 0,1 %, the effect of F would be "very highly significant". However it should be noticed that a "significant" effect of F means that the average values of P are "significantly" different ; it does not mean that one is much higher than the other one or that F is highly efficient.

In the case of SAFFIL reinforcement, despite the fact that infiltration has been very good as illustrated in figure 5 partial debonding occurs during the tensile test (figure 6). Large silica particules (probably from the binder used to manufacture the fiber inserts) are also present amongst the fibers as shown in figure 7. Those products show up to be very notch sensitive and elongations to failure which are not reported in the tables are always under 1 %. From table IV, one can draw the following conclusions : the smallest significant difference at the significant level of 1 % between two yield stress being 21 MPa, we can conclude that SAFFIL is highly significantly reinforcing the yield stress of Al-Si12-Cu-Ni.

Concerning the UTS, the scattering of experimental data is too important to allow any conclusions.

Young's modulus is highly significantly increased when volume fraction of fibers is higher than 0,05.

Fig.5 SAFFIL reinforces Al-Si12-Cu-Ni
Microstructure showing good infiltration

In the case of SiC whiskers, infiltration again is very good but wetting is not perfect and debonding also occurs as illustrated in figures 8 and 9. However in that case the results are much more uniform and for exemple, the smallest significant difference at a significant level of 1 % between two values of the yield stress is only 8.3 MPa ; in fact, the effect of an addition of SiC, at a volume fraction of 12 %, on the yield stress is very highly significant. If there is no significant increase between 12 % and 16 % of fibers, 20 % again gives a new highly significant increase over 12 %.

The same type of results are obtained for the Young's modulus. As for the UTS, as with SAFFIL, the material reveals to be very notch sensitive and premature failures occur on machining grooves and the dispersion of results is rather large. Even though it is not possible to draw conclusions on the influence of volume fraction of fibers, one can notice that presence of SiC increases highly significantly the UTS of the matrix.

Fig.6 Al-Si12-Cu-Ni + 20 % SAFFIL fiber debonding on fracture surface

Fig.7 Al-Si12-Cu-Ni + 20 % SAFFIL site of large SiO₂ inclusion on a fracture surface

Fig.8 Al-Si12-Cu-Ni + 16 % SiC : fracture surface

Fig.9 Al-Si12-Cu-Ni + 16 % SiC : fracture surface whisker pull out

High temperature behaviour

For those experiments, the results are much more uniform and a common experimental standard deviation can be evaluated : 5,8 MPa (with 36 degrees of freedom) for either UTS or yield stress. Young's modulus have not been measured in those experiments. Tables VI, VII and figures 10, 11, 12, 13 show the data obtained in this investigation.

Table VI. Yield stress and U.T.S. of Al-Si12-Cu-Ni reinforced with I.C.I. SAFFIL at different temperatures

Fiber volume fraction	350°C		300°C		250°C	
	YS (MPa)	UTS (MPa)	YS (MPa)	UTS (MPa)	YS (MPa)	UTS (MPa)
0	35	55	n.m.	70	70	115
0,05	54	63	79	88	112	134
0,12	68	74	not measured		not measured	
0,20	110	112	154	155	186	198

Table VII. Yield stress and U.T.S. of Al-Si12-Cu-Ni reinforced with SiC whiskers (TOKAI) at different temperatures

Fiber volume fraction	350°C		300°C		250°C	
	YS (MPa)	UTS (MPa)	YS (MPa)	UTS (MPa)	YS (MPa)	UTS (MPa)
0	35	55	n.m.	70	70	115
0,12	94	124	153	180	197	226
0,16	120	147	not measured		not measured	
0,20	163	181	207	235	268	284

For both case an analysis of variance made either on the yield stress or on the UTS shows very highly significant effects of temperature, volume fraction of fibers and a slight interaction temperature composition.

Yield stress. The effect of reinforcement is very highly significant and 20 % of SAFFIL have the same effect as 12 % SiC whiskers at all temperatures (table VIII).

Fig.10 0,2 % YS vs. temperature and volume fraction of fibers for SAFFIL reinforced Al-Si12-Cu-Ni

Fig.11 UTS vs. temperature and volume fraction of fibers for SAFFIL reinforced Al-Si12-Cu-Ni

Fig.12 0,2 % YS vs. temperature and volume fraction of fibers for SiC reinforced Al-Si12-Cu-Ni

Fig.13 UTS vs. temperature and volume fraction of fibers for SiC reinforced Al-Si12-Cu-Ni

Table VIII . Yield stress of Al-Si12-Cu-Ni reinforced with 20 % SAFFIL or 12 % SiC whiskers at different temperatures

Temperature (°C)	YS (MPa)	For comparison yield stress of the matrix (MPa)
250	192 ± 8	70
300	153 ± 8	not measured
350	102 ± 8	35

There is a linear effect of temperature. The difference between 350°C and 300°C is the same than the difference between 300°C and 250°C and is equal to 43 ± 6 MPa. The yield stress at 250°C of the unreinforced matrix is equal to the one of 12 % SAFFIL reinforced Al-Si12-Cu-Ni at 350°C. For a temperature increase of 50 C, when SAFFIL increases the properties by 33 ± 10 MPa, the same amount of SiC whiskers will increase the properties by 52 ± 10 MPa.

U.T.S. The reinforcement is again very highly significant and there is a linear temperature dependance. An increase of 50°C leads to a drop of 45 ± 6 MPa of the U.T.S. The observations made on the yield stress are also valid here. For exemple UTS of Al-Si12-Cu-Ni at 250°C is equal to UTS of Al-Si12-Cu-Ni + 12 % SAFFIL at 350°C.

Fatigue properties

The fatigue limits at 10^7 cycles obtained through a staircase analysis are given in table IX.

Table IX. Fatigue limits of reinforced Al-Si12-Cu-Ni

Material	Fatigue limit (MPa)	Standard deviation (MPa)
Al-Si12-Cu-Ni	80	2
Al-Si12-Cu-Ni + 20 % SAFFIL	109	2
Al-Si12-Cu-Ni+20% SiC whiskers	131	4

This table shows that a noticeable improvement is obtained on the fatigue limit of this material.

Conclusions

Metal matrix composites of an aluminium-silicon matrix and alumina fibers (5 % to 20 % volume fraction) or SiC whiskers (12 % to 20 % volume fraction) have been obtained using a squeeze casting technique.

Mechanical properties have been measured at different temperature from room temperature up to 350°C.

At room temperature, despite a large scattering in the results which prevents from drawing any conclusion about any improvement of UTS, a significant increase of the modulus and the yield stress has been obtained with both type of reinforcement.

At higher temperature, results are more homogeneous and it is possible to gain 100°C in service temperature in the range 250°C - 350°C by adding an appropriate amount of fibers. Indeed mechanical properties of reinforced products at 350°C have been found to be equal to those of the unreinforced matrix at 250°C.

For that purpose 12 % volume fraction of SiC whiskers would give an equivalent results to 20 % volume fraction of alumina fibers. This result is not surprising when one takes into account the mechanical properties of the two different fibers.

Substantial improvements of properties have been obtained with both fibers. Selection of one type of reinforcement would depend on a matter of price and other properties such as thermal conductivity, wear resistance, corrosion behaviour and so on.

References

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